

RESEARCH OUTPUT MANAGEMENT THROUGH
OPEN ACCESS INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES IN
PALESTINIAN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRAINING BOOKLET

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INTRODUCTION

Educational and Training Preparation Work Package in the ROMOR Project aims at:

- Developing tailored training to increase capacity among Palestinian (PS) research support staff for designing, implementing, operating, populating, and sustaining Open Access Institutional Repositories (OAIRs);
- Equipping PS research support staff to deliver training on research output management to researchers at their own institutions.

Based on a survey of existing curricula in digital preservation/curation, and lessons learned from the series of training events and lecturing activities by partner EU HEIs as well as the feedback obtained from the needs assessment study (WP1) and the planned workshop (WP3), the education material has been prepared and will be submitted to partner PS HEIs.

In addition, the resources made available by European Projects LERU, LEARN and 4C were used.

A primary source is the DCC how to guides for RDM

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guide>

Foster (Facilitate Open Science training for European Research), 23 libraries for RDM and Mantra University of Edinburgh courses have also been inspiring this booklet.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF ROMOR TRAINING

The main goal of this vocational curriculum is to build capacity in implementing institutional repositories, and in technically and operationally managing these repositories.

ROMOR partners have agreed to employ the DCC's RDM service model to structure our training including an emphasis on:

- softer infrastructure aspects including policies, business planning and training;

- more technical infrastructure requirements which are based around the data lifecycle.

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/developing-rdm-services>

This booklet delineates the key concepts and definitions associated with the DCC cycle and RDM service model, providing a clear and succinct introduction for those new to the area.

This booklet also explores the full range of activities and tools to be developed for sharing and re-using research outputs and is in three parts:

- **Data governance:** policy and leadership, cost models; infrastructure;
- **Data management:** data curation lifecycle activities, from the design of good data through content creator management, metadata creation, ingest into a repository, repository management, access policies and implementation, to data reuse;
- **Data literacy:** skills training and advocacy issues.

In May 2016, the Competitiveness Council Conclusions called for full open access to scientific publications in Europe by 2020. On 21 June 2017, the European Commission set-up the new High Level Expert Group European Open Science Cloud. Its mission is to advise the Commission on the measures needed to implement the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable/ Re-producible (FAIR) data is an integral part in the process of opening up science and research. By improving the FAIR-ness of research data it will unlock the potential for both scientific research and society to draw from the benefits of this data, and also enable significant contribution to economic growth.

EOSC: RDM in Europe is the recent publication of the Commission's High Level Expert Group Report on the European Open Science Cloud

More information:

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm>

RDM Policy and Strategy

RDM Policy and Strategy aspects of good practice:

- Being clear on what constitutes research and research data
- Equating RDM to good research
- Clearly stated roles and responsibilities
- Stressing a 'proportionate' amount of effort

Getting started: enjoy these short video-interviews and find some resources on policies and strategy

Peter Suber video interviews on recommendations for OA policies and sharing

<http://openmedproject.eu/peter-suber/>

Progress toward full OA must take into account many issues, and policy support is needed. Case studies and best practice can give inspiration.

LERU has prepared a Roadmap for Research Data (2012)

http://www.leru.org/files/publications/AP14_LERU_Roadmap_for_Research_data_final.pdf

LEARN (LEaders Activating Research Networks) has realized a model RDM policy and a [Toolkit of Best Practice Case Studies in RDM](#) together with a [Self-Assessment Tool](#)

The Library of the University of Vienna (leader of Work Package 3 of LEARN) collected and analysed over 40 European RDM policies in 2015/2016 and realized an [Evaluation Grid](#).

All the [LEARN deliverables](#) can be downloaded here: <http://learn-rdm.eu/en/about/>

Case studies of RDM policies and requirements

Overview of funders' data policies

www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/policy-and-legal/overview-funders-data-policies

RCUK Common Principles on Data Policy

www.rcuk.ac.uk/research/Pages/DataPolicy.aspx

Learn (2017) Model Policy for Research Data Management (RDM) at Research Institutions/Institutes:

Identify at least 3 issues which may limit your ability to share research outputs.

Data Management Planning

Data Management Plan aspects of good practice:

- Linking data management planning to related policies and processes (avoid duplication of effort, conflicts)
- Location of data management support information on research staff pages
- Briefing Grants and Contracts staff about processes
- Considering the costs of RDM
- Linking to external resources where necessary

One example is the DMPTool that lists funder requirements in the United States and builds a plan by asking the researcher to answer a series of questions.

<https://dmptool.org>

Other countries such as the U.K. and Canada have similar tools for Data Management Plans

DCC

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans>

DMPT Online: Data Management Planning Tool.

<http://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

DataOne

Data Management Plans.

<https://www.dataone.org/plans>

ICPSR

Framework for Creating a Data Management Plan

<http://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/content/data-management/dmp/framework.html>

Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)
Libraries, Data Management and Publishing

<http://libraries.mit.edu/guides/subjects/data-management/index.html>

Ball, A., & Duke, M. (2015). 'How to Cite Datasets and Link to Publications'. DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>

Choose a dataset here: <http://www.re3data.org/> and describe it according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>

DATA MANAGEMENT

Getting started: Understanding the life of research data with the DCC Curation Lifecycle Model,

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-lifecycle-model>

ROMOR training is based on DDC RDM services models, matched with PS HE educational needs and following EDISON Competencies framework for the 3 different levels of proficiency: Introductory (Familiarity), Intermediate (Usage), Advanced (Assess). ROMOR training is produced to reflect the findings of EU HE good practice and the PS HE needs assessment work package (WP1).

Managing Active Data

Managing active data aspects of good practice:

- Understanding your storage needs
- Reviewing internal systems and processes to optimise RDM services and efficiencies
- Being aware of services from external providers (risks, benefits)
- Choosing flexible solutions that scale

Knowledge of:

- Metadata standards and schemas for repository, data formats, identifiers, data citation, data licensing.
- Domain ontologies, taxonomies, knowledge of the semantic web and linked data; skills in Resource Description Framework (RDF)
- Discovery tools

Metadata

Getting started: Determine what metadata format is appropriate and standard to recommend or apply by using the [Metadata Standards Directory](http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/standards/) of RDA (Research Data Alliance)

<http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/standards/>

This website contains a comprehensive set of metadata standards covering general metadata standards, such as Dublin Core for describing digital objects, and PREMIS for defining preservation metadata, as well as a very wide range of subject specific metadata.

Citing Data

Getting started: [DataCite](https://www.datacite.org) has resources to help researchers make their datasets citable to help users give attribution and to begin measuring impact by issuing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for datasets

<https://www.datacite.org>

FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES

<https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>

Jones, S., Pryor, G. & Whyte, A. (2013). 'How to Develop Research Data Management Services - a guide for HEIs'. DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre.

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>

What research outputs will you collect or create, how will it be created, and for what purpose? The planning process for data management begins with a data planning checklist:

http://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/resource/DM_P_Checklist_2013.pdf

Data Selection and Handover

Data selection and handover aspects of good practice:

- Being clear on what data might need to be retained and why (reproducibility, validation)
- Being clear about how long the data needs to be retained
- Helping researchers to be clear about any restrictions on access
- Being clear on who to contact to help with selection and appraisal (consider how and when re-appraisal may need to happen)

Ability to select and appraise datasets

Whyte, A. & Wilson, A. (2010). "How to Appraise and Select Research Data for Curation". DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre.

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>

MIT Libraries. (2014) Data management and publishing: Organize your files. Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <http://libraries.mit.edu/data-management/store/organize>

Choose a publication here:

<https://www.openaire.eu/search/find> and describe it according to the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories:

<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/index.html>

Data Repositories

Data repositories aspects of good practice:

- Clear policy on acquisition (limits on size, formats, sensitivity)
- Provision of a unique digital identifier (DOI)
- Provide advice on external, discipline specific repositories (re3data.org)
- Being clear about any normalisation processes that may occur upon ingest (can affect usability of deposited data)
- Advising on how to link data to related publications
- Guidance on how to cite data that has been deposited (generated on deposit where feasible)

Because of the growing importance of the research repository in the data deluge age, it is imperative to examine data repositories current state and potential challenges.

Digital preservation

Understand vocabularies and standards for digital archives using the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) reference model and trustworthy digital repository certifications such as ISO 16363 and the Data Seal of Approval

Find tools that are available to help with digital preservation using COPTR, http://coptr.digipres.org/Main_Page

Trusted Digital Repositories: Attributes and Responsibilities OCLC (2002)

<https://www.oclc.org/content/dam/research/activities/trustedrep/repositories.pdf>

COAR ROADMAP (2015)

https://www.coar-repositories.org/files/Roadmap_final_formatted_20150203.pdf

What do you think would be the advantages of storing your research outputs on the central, or Department networked repository?

Data Catalogues

Data catalogues aspects of good practice:

- Ability to register and describe data sets
- Ability to link to related publications in OAIRs, journals or external repositories
- Encouraging researchers to register for ORCIDi
- Making use of internal grant IDs when describing research outputs
- Making use of data held in other systems to reduce burden by automating description (CRIS systems, institutional publications repository)

Data catalogues include knowledge of:

Existing data centres, repositories and collections and data discovery mechanisms

Data manipulation and analysis techniques and tools

The way data are organized and structured within collections

Access

Find an appropriate repository by searching the re3data.org registry of research data repositories

Publish and share data now using free, online data repositories such as [figshare](http://figshare.com), [Zenodo](http://zenodo.org), [Open Science Framework](http://OpenScienceFramework.org), or [DataVerse](http://DataVerse.org)

Databib list of research data repositories

<http://databib.org>

Data licensing and privacy

Getting started: Understand the importance of data licensing and learn about Creative Commons.

Listen to this video about Intellectual Property Right (University of Minnesota. Research Data management course Module 4: Data Access and Ownership)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xTETUeHZmCU>

How to License Research Data from the Digital Curation Centre can help librarians work with researchers to choose a license for the data they share

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides/license-research-data>

JISC manages the DATAPROTECTION email list with discussions on issues related to sensitive data

<https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?AO=data-protection>

Find tools that are available to help with digital preservation using COPTR,

http://coptr.digipres.org/Main_Page

European Commission (EC). (2014). Protection of databases. Last updated 07 June 2016. ec.europa.eu/internal_market/copyright/prot-databases/index_en.htm

Ball, A. (2014). 'How to License Research Data'. DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides/license-research-data

Think about the research you are conducting. Identify the people and organizations with an interest in the data resulting from your research, and describe what rights each have with respect to the research outputs.

Getting started: Given the increasing attention to managing, publishing, and preserving research datasets as scholarly assets, what competencies in working with research data will graduate students in STEM disciplines need to be successful in their fields.

And what role can librarians play in helping students attain these competencies?

Data literacy is the ability to read, create and communicate data as information and has been formally described in varying ways (Wikimedia)

Data information literacy (DIL) has a more expansive definition and concerns the activities of the data creator and consumer. DIL (Data Information Literacy) is a working space for the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) funded research project investigating data information literacy (DIL) needs of e-scientists.

The term “data information literacy” has been adopted with the deliberate intent of tying two emerging roles for librarians together. By viewing information literacy and data services as complementary rather than separate activities, the DIL project seeks to leverage the progress made and the lessons learned in each service area.

<http://www.datainfolit.org/publications/>

They identified twelve competencies associated with DIL:

- Databases and data format
- Discovery and Acquisition of Data
- Data Management and Organization
- Data Conversion and Interoperability

Quality Assurance
Metadata
Data Curation and Re-use
Cultures of Practice
Data Preservation
Data Analysis
Data Visualization
Ethics, including citation of data

The Data Information Literacy project developed a curriculum to help librarians and other teachers incorporate data into information literacy outreach and instruction,

<http://www.datainfolit.org/publications/>

Advocacy

Who undertakes advocacy and what is the message?

Getting started: enjoy this short video on the importance of sharing

Data Sharing and Management Snafu in 3 Short Acts

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N2zK3sAtr-4>

Data carpentry

People understand the need for computer and data skills. Data Carpentry develops and teaches workshops on the fundamental data skills needed to conduct research. Data Carpentry workshops are domain-specific, so that we are teaching researchers the skills most relevant to their domain and using examples from their type of work. [Data Carpentry](#) is a sibling organization of Software Carpentry

<http://www.datacarpentry.org>

New England Collaborative Data Management Curriculum (NECDMC)

<http://library.umassmed.edu/necdmc/index>

DataONE education modules

<https://www.dataone.org/education-modules>

LIBER

A “top ten” list of recommendations for libraries to get started with research data management

<http://libereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/The%20research%20data%20group%202012%20v7%20final.pdf>

Relevant concepts are presented and mapped in the e-Science Thesaurus,

<http://bit.ly/RDAthing2>

Training materials for librarians and archivists

UNC-Chapel Hill and University of Edinburgh (2016)

Coursera MOOC (Massively Open Online Course)
Research Data Management

<https://www.coursera.org/learn/data-management>

DIY Training Kit for Librarians, University of Edinburgh

<http://datalib.edina.ac.uk/mantra/libtraining.html>

RDMRose Lite, University of Sheffield

<http://rdmrose.group.shef.ac.uk>

23 Things: Libraries for Research Data.

All program resources and materials have been released under a Creative Commons license in 23 Things re-purpose toolkit.

<http://www.ands.org.au/partners-and-communities/23-research-data-things/toolkit>

Data Curation Profiles (DCP) - Project by the Purdue University Libraries and the Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign. [DCP Toolkit](#) enables librarians and faculty members to work together to collaboratively create data management plans for research projects.

<http://datacurationprofiles.org>

The Data Information Literacy Toolkit was the interview instrument developed and used by the Data Information Literacy project to better understand the educational needs of graduate students in managing, working with and curating their data sets.

<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/dilsymposium/2013/interviewinstruments/1/>

Purdue University Library

Begin a conversation with a researcher about data by Conducting a Data Interview,

http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1092&context=lib_research

Learn more about a researcher's needs by reading or creating your own Data Curation Profile,

<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/dcp/>

University of Minnesota Engineering Section.

Data management course: This short course on data management is designed for graduate students in the engineering disciplines who seek to prepare themselves as "data information literate" scientists in the digital research environment.

https://sites.google.com/a/umn.edu/data-management-course_structures/home-1

Develop engagement materials

DataOne Librarian Outreach Kit

<http://bit.ly/RDAthing9>

DataQ forum: Questions about data answered by experts

<http://researchdataq.org>

Witt, M., Carlson, J., Brandt, D.S., & Cragin, M.H. (2009) "Developing the Data Curation Profiles" International Journal of Digital Curation, 4(3), 93-103.

<http://www.ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc/article/view/137>

Megan R. Sapp Nelson, "A Pilot Competency Matrix for Data Management Skills: A Step toward the Development of Systematic Data Information Literacy Programs," Journal of eScience Librarianship 6, no. 1 (2017).

<http://escholarship.umassmed.edu/jeslib/vol6/iss1/1>

Michael Witt (2016) 23 Things: Libraries for Research Data

<http://dx.doi.org/10.15497/RDA00005>

Witt, M., Carlson, J., Brandt, D.S., & Cragin, M.H. (2009) "Developing the Data Curation Profiles" International Journal of Digital Curation, 4(3), 93-103.

<http://www.ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc/article/view/137>

Plan a Data Literacy Course using the following Course Alignment matrix:

<https://goo.gl/JjLZc8>

REFERENCES TO GUIDANCE, TOOLS AND RESOURCES

- Read the most current literature in the Digital Curation Bibliography, <http://digital-scholarship.org/dcbw/dcbw.htm>
- Dozens of examples of resource guides created by librarians for patrons to learn more about data on the SpringShare LibGuide Community Site <http://community.libguides.com>
- International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC) <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/international-digital-curation-conference-idcc>
- Research Data Access & Preservation Summit (RDAP) <https://www.facebook.com/ResearchDataAccessPreservation>
- International Association for Social Science and Information Services & Technology (IASSIST) <http://www.iassistdata.org>
- Research Data Alliance (RDA) <https://www.rd-alliance.org>
- DCC Glossary <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/digital-curation/glossary>
- DCC Curation Reference Manual <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-reference-manual/completed-chapters>
- DCC How-To Guides <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>
- DCC Briefing Papers <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/briefing-papers>
- UK Data Archive: Managing and sharing data: best practice for researchers <http://www.data-archive.ac.uk/media/2894/managingsharing.pdf>
- You might also like to join our Data Librarians Google Group so you can connect with others who share your interest in research data, <https://plus.google.com/u/0/communities/105455769899183786145>